

A/Miz.51 and PMS3 A/Saruchina were more efficient at flowering. PMS3 A/Saruchina recorded the highest total dry matter (12.1 t/ha) and grain yield (538 g/m²)

Fertilizer management

Integrated effect of deeply placed urea and *Gliricidia* green manure on grain yield of transplanted rice

S. S. Dhane, R. R. Khadse, and H. K. Pawar, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Karjat, Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli, Maharashtra 410201, India

We studied the integrated effect of organic and inorganic sources of N on grain yield of rice variety PLG-1 (130 d duration) during 1991-93 wet seasons. We compared how deeply placing urea behind the plow and applying *Gliricidia sepium* leaves as a green manure—individually and in combination—affected rainfed transplanted rice.

Each of the nine treatments in the experiment was laid out in a 50-m² plot on the RARS farm in a randomized block design with three replications. The soil was clay loam with pH 7.4 (1:2.5 soil:water) and a cation exchange capacity of 35 meq/100 g soil. All of the plots received 21 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 41 kg K/ha as potassium chloride.

Prilled urea (PU) (25 kg N and 50 kg N/ha) was applied behind the plow, about 5-6 cm deep, at the time of puddling. *Gliricidia* was spread uniformly over newly puddled soil as fresh green manure at 5 and 10 t/ha (containing 2.7% N on an oven-dry basis)

Effect of integrated use of inorganic and organic N on grain yield of rice. Maharashtra, India.

followed by IR64 A/Miz.51. Photosynthesis at flowering, however, was positively correlated with total dry matter ($r = 0.430^*$) and grain yield ($r = 0.446^*$) at harvest.

Unlike PMS3 A/Saruchina, high Pn coupled with low MR and high Pn/MR are desirable for high photosynthetic productivity, which ultimately leads to more grain. ■

Effect of deeply placed urea behind the plow and *Gliricidia* green manure on grain yield of transplanted rice. Maharashtra, India. 1991-93 wet seasons.

Treatment			Mean grain yield (t/ha)			
Urea N (kg/ha)	Green manure (t/ha)	(kg N/ha)	1991	1992	1993	Pooled mean
0	0	0	4.0	2.2	3.7	3.3
25	0	0	4.9	2.8	4.4	4.0
50	0	0	4.5	3.9	3.9	4.1
0	5	31.5	5.0	2.5	4.2	3.9
0	10	63.0	4.8	3.0	4.8	4.2
25	5	31.5	5.2	3.5	4.8	4.5
25	10	63.0	4.9	3.9	5.1	4.6
50	5	31.5	5.0	4.6	4.7	4.8
50	10	63.0	5.4	4.8	5.5	5.2
LSD (0.05)			ns ^a	0.4	0.4	0.1

^ans = not significant.

and pressed below the surface by hand. Three-week-old rice seedlings were planted at 20- × 15-cm² spacing during the wet season on 24 Jul 1991, 20 Jul 1992, and 19 Jul 1993 and harvested on 10 Nov 1991, 5 Nov 1992, and 3 Nov 1993.

The response of the rice crop to the different treatments varied significantly with the season (see table). Applying *Gliricidia* at 5 or 10 t/ha coupled with the deep placement of urea at 25 or 50 kg N/ha

increased rice grain yield significantly over applying *Gliricidia* alone. The maximum yield of 5.2 t/ha, which was significantly higher than the rest, was obtained by applying *Gliricidia* at 10 t/ha and urea at 50 kg N/ha (see table, figure). Thus, the integrated use of inorganic and organic nitrogen can make important contributions to increasing and sustaining rice production. ■

Effect of rice hull, biofertilizer, and chemical fertilizers on growth and nitrogen economy of wetland rice

T. K. Biswas, National Facility for Blue-Green Algal Collection, Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi 110012, India; and R. N. Garg, Agricultural Physics Department, IARI

We studied the effects on rice yield of using leucaena (*Leucaena leucifera*), a common leguminous plant in northern India; blue-green algae (BGA); and urea—individually and in combination—in a mild alkaline soil with and without rice hull amendment.

The soil was sandy loam (mixed, Isohyperthermic Typic Ustocrept) with pH 8.0, EC 4.2 dS/m, 22 kg ESP, CEC 15 cmol_c/kg, and 0.46% organic C. Rice hull (0.56% N on an oven-dry basis) was incorporated at 5 t/ha (about 22 kg N)

Effect of integrated use of biofertilizer and chemical fertilizer N on yield of Pusa Basmati 1. IARI, New Delhi, India. 1992 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Rice hull-amended field	Untreated field
Control	3.5	3.4
Blue-green algae (BGA)	3.9	3.8
Leucaena	4.9	4.7
Urea (30 kg N/ha)	3.8	4.0
Urea (60 kg N/ha)	4.4	4.1
Urea (120 kg N/ha)	5.1	5.0
Leucaena + BGA	4.9	4.7
Urea (30 kg N/ha) + BGA	4.6	3.9
Urea (60 kg N/ha) + BGA	5.0	4.8
1/2 Leucaena + urea (60 kg N/ha)	5.2	4.7
1/2 Leucaena + urea (90 kg N/ha)	5.4	5.0
CD (0.05)	0.4	0.5
Pooled mean	4.6	4.3
CD (0.05)		(0.7)

during land preparation at the IARI farm during the 1992 kharif (wet) season. Fresh leucaena (2.3% N on an oven-dry basis) was chopped into 2-3 cm lengths and incorporated at 30 t/ha (about 90 kg N) 3 d before transplanting. Soil-based inocula of BGA (*Aulosira*, *Tolypothrix*, *Scytonema*, *Nostoc*, *Anabaena*, and *Plectonema*) at 30 kg/ha were broadcast at 8 d after transplanting (DT) on standing water. Prilled urea was applied in three splits at transplanting, 35 DT, and at flowering.

Pooled data showed that rice hull did not significantly increase the grain yield of Pusa Basmati 1, although a constant increase in grain yield was obtained by adding rice hull regardless of different BGA, leucaena, and

prilled urea treatments (see table). BGA and urea at both 30 and 60 kg N/ha had synergistic effects in fields that received rice hull. In untreated fields, a synergistic effect was observed only for urea at 60 kg N and in BGA treatments.

The significant yield increase achieved with BGA and urea combinations when compared with similar levels of urea alone suggests that a starter dose of fertilizer N is important for establishing BGA in mild alkaline soil. Results revealed that BGA contributed about 30 kg N/ha when applied with urea to plots where rice hull was added. No such synergistic effect was noticed with the leucaena and BGA combination. However, cuttings of leucaena

increased rice yield by more than 1 t/ha, with or without rice hull.

In northern India, sandy loam soils with low organic matter content are generally poor, both physically and in N status. Rice has been grown increasingly in this region during the past three decades, with burning of hulls near rice mills a common practice. Instead, hulls could be applied on the fields to improve the overall soil physical property and organic matter status. We suggest that farmers should apply rice hulls, combined with leucaena and BGA, to substantially cut down on costly fertilizer N use while improving the soil. ■

Fertilizer management-organic sources

Influence of intercropping green manure in wet seeded rice

P. Jayapaul, B. Uthayakumar, and S. Purushothaman, Agricultural College and Research Institute (ACRI), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

The effects of incorporating intercropped green manure (GM) in wet seeded rice cultivated during 1992-94 were studied at ACRI.

The soil was a sandy clay loam classified as Typic Ultisol. The initial nutrient status was 233 kg N/ha, 17.1 kg P/ha, and 246 kg K/ha in 1992-93 and 226 kg N/ha, 16.2 kg

P/ha, and 244 kg K/ha in 1993-94. *Sesbania rostrata* usually has delayed germination when sown under puddled conditions. so instead, it was raised separately and 20-d-old seedlings were planted. Seeds of *S. speciosa* were dibbled at 3 kg/ha.

Five days after IR20 was sown, both GMs were intercropped in the main field in the empty space of 30 cm and maintained at a 1.5-m interval. Intra-row spacings of 15 and 30 cm and incorporation at 30 and 45 d after planting (DAP)/sowing for the GMs were compared with a no-GM control in a randomized block design with three replications. Fresh green biomass was assessed at incorporation.

More green biomass was obtained when *S. rostrata* seedlings were planted at 15 cm spacing and incorporated 45 DAP than with the other treatments. When compared with the no-GM control, the yield increase with this method was 38.4% more in 1992-93 and 44.5% more in 1993-94. Because of its initial slow growth rate, *S. speciosa* biomass was lower than that of *S. rostrata*. Incorporating green biomass in the standing ricefield positively increased the yield parameters of panicle number, panicle length, and filled grains per panicle, resulting in higher rice yield (see table).

Wet seeded rice benefits from intercropping 20-d-old *S. rostrata* seedlings at intra-row spacing of 15 cm and incorporation at 45 DAP. ■

Effect of intra-row spacing and time of incorporation of green manure on biomass production, yield parameters, and yield of wet seeded rice. ACRI. Madurai, India. 1992-94.

Green manure	Treatments		1992-93						1993-94					
	Intra-row spacing (cm)	Time of incorporation (DAP) ^a	Fresh green biomass (t/ha)	N input (kg/ha)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grams/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Fresh green biomass (t/ha)	N input (kg/ha)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Sesbania rostrata</i>	15	30	1.30	42.9	8.0	18.2	90.0	3.96	1.23	38.7	7.4	17.3	87.1	3.59
	15	45	1.64	53.5	8.0	18.3	91.1	4.04	1.50	49.2	7.6	17.3	88.2	3.80
	30	30	1.05	34.8	7.8	18.2	88.0	3.61	0.88	29.4	7.0	17.0	87.1	3.51
	30	45	0.76	25.4	7.4	18.0	85.1	3.51	0.73	24.5	6.8	17.1	86.2	3.51
<i>Sesbania speciosa</i>	15	30	0.14	3.6	7.2	17.7	83.3	3.31	0.13	3.4	6.4	16.8	85.2	3.22
	15	45	0.18	4.5	7.2	17.6	83.2	3.22	0.18	4.5	6.4	16.8	85.1	3.10
	30	30	0.07	1.9	7.2	17.4	83.1	3.04	0.06	1.6	6.2	16.2	83.1	2.92
	30	45	0.09	2.5	7.0	17.4	83.1	2.98	0.08	2.3	6.0	16.2	82.5	2.87
No green manure	-	-	-	-	7.0	17.0	80.1	2.92	-	-	4.8	16.0	78.3	2.63
CD (P = 0.05)	-	-	-	-	ns	0.2	0.9	0.17	-	-	0.8	0.7	0.2	0.40

^aDAP = days after planting.